

Predicting Oxygen Utilization & Nurse Staffing Needs For SARS-CoV-2

Satori Iwamoto, Bahaar Kaur Muhar, Ashwin Sidhu, Harrison Chu, Michelle Chiu, Heidi Spantzel, Hillary Chu, Norah Zhou, Arnold Spantzel, Eric Zhang, Gary Chu, MD

Abstract: Supplemental oxygen is an essential part of in-hospital care for most patients hospitalized with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia. This study seeks to identify hospitalized patients who will require advanced oxygen support (high flow oxygen, CPAP, BiPAP, or mechanical ventilation) within 96 hours of admission using a machine learning model. This information can be useful for hospitals to plan for nurse staffing, as patients will consume more resources and will need more staff assistance.

Data from 302 SARS-CoV-2 patients was used to create a classifier to predict whether or not patients would require advanced oxygen support within 96 hours of admission. Of the 302 cases, 211 were randomly selected to train the model, and 91 were randomly selected for testing. Through a labeled dataset, we performed supervised learning by using a random forest ensemble model which included demographic, clinical comorbidities, vitals, and laboratory values. We used 5-fold cross-validation to evaluate our trained model and employed a majority vote decision across the five trained models in order to produce the final prediction for a given patient. Through the models, we yielded results through sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and F1 score with the 91 cases of training data. An additional 24 cases were used to test the validity of the ensemble consensus model. Approximately 40% of all patients progressed to require advanced oxygen support 96 hours after the initial presentation. Although the insight gained from the model may not definitively predict the course of an individual patient, this model may help hospital administrators plan for staffing needs with a 48-hour lead time. Patients on high oxygen support require high acuity beds, which have increased nurse-to-patient ratios. Additional samples may increase its statistical significance. Nevertheless, this model demonstrates the potential and viability of using data science to help manage hospital resources.

Keywords: COVID-19, nurse staffing, resource management, machine learning, oxygen utilization

I. INTRODUCTION

During the peak phase of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic, hospitals were inundated with critical patients requiring a significant amount of oxygen to sustain life. Oxygen and oxygen delivering devices became limited commodities [1]. The logistics of keeping the oxygen supply above the demand can be challenging. Being able to predict a hospital's oxygen needs may help the administration navigate through the oxygen supply chain. For example, Remdesivir, an antiviral medication without a statistically known significant decrease in mortality, was given FDA approval to treat SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) because it showed significant efficacy in decreasing the length of hospital stay [2]. which reduced overall oxygen resource consumption. If we can identify which patient will crash and require advanced oxygen life support (high flow oxygen, cPAP, biPAP, ventilators, etc.) 96 hours later from the time of admission, then the hospital will have sufficient lead time to ensure proper oxygen resources, equipment, and human resources are available to meet the needs of the

patient.

II. Literature Review

Coronaviruses are a family of viruses responsible for many illnesses among humans and animals. It is a pleomorphic, single-stranded positive sense RNA virus that is responsible for common community-acquired colds with symptoms affecting the upper respiratory tract as well as gastro-intestinal tract in both the adult and pediatric population [3]. Coronaviruses are mRNA viruses whose name derives from their crown-like shape in electron micrographs [4]. Some of the more notorious members of this family of coronaviruses include Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) and severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV). SARS-CoV is deadly, with a case-fatality rate of 15 percent [5]. MERS-CoV was even deadlier at 35% [6]. SARS-CoV-2's mortality rate is still evolving. But the consensus is roughly 3 percent of those infected are seriously ill [7]. A quick literature search suggests a wide range of mortality among hospitalized patients: 15% [8], 31% [9] and 50% [10]. Per autopsy report, most of the deaths

caused by SARS-CoV-2 were due to respiratory failure from adult respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)[11] Once a patient developed adult respiratory distress syndrome from SARS-CoV-2, the mortality is high, nearly 40% [12]. Besides causing respiratory failures, SARS-CoV-2 can cause hypercoagulable state [13], leading to ischemic stroke, even among young patients who are otherwise healthy and free of respiratory symptoms [14]. One theory suggested that the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 may activate the alternative complement pathway, and injure the endothelial cells in hospitalized SARS-CoV-2 patients [15]. Cytokine storms and Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) observed in hospitalized SARS-CoV-2 patients can also contribute to the hypercoagulable state. Ischemic strokes from SARS-CoV-2 can further increase the complications, morbidity, and mortality rate of SARS-CoV-2.

There are several risk factors generally recognized by the medical community that are associated with adverse outcomes-- advanced age, cancer, chronic kidney disease, diabetes, obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²), poor cardiac function, solid organ or stem cell transplantation, immunosuppression, and other chronic lung diseases [16]. As the virus evolves and vaccines are introduced, advanced age has become less of a risk factor [17].

Like many illnesses, SARS-CoV-2 can leave life-lasting marks on a patient's health with nonspecific symptoms [18]. It may take many years to decipher this nebulous sequela, like those associated with the Gulf War syndrome [19], or the World Trade Center Syndrome [20].

When studying the number of severe SARS-CoV-2 cases during the pandemic, the number of patients in the ICU do not correlate with the total number of cases. The maximum number of SARS-CoV-2 patients occupied in the ICU have been roughly the same across different waves of the pandemic [21]. This may, in fact, be due to the limited number of available beds in the individual hospital's ICU. Therefore, we must use an alternative method to measure the number of patients severely ill with the infection. We proposed to study the number of patients on advanced oxygen support instead of patients in the ICU to more accurately measure severity.

III. Methodology

We collected data from 302 SARS-CoV-2 patients admitted to a community hospital between August and September of 2020 in order to conduct this study. The patients' data was de-identified to maintain their privacy. We then implemented the data science pipeline to train our final model. We used Python tools and libraries to plot histograms and pie charts which

allowed us to determine outliers and identify trends which helped us clean the data. Data reformatting was performed to make the dataset more machine-friendly for further analysis.

211 of the 302 cases were randomly selected to train the model, and 91 cases were randomly selected for testing. Inclusion criteria included all patients with a positive diagnosis of the SARS-CoV-2 test who had been admitted to Kaiser South Sacramento from August 2020 to September 2020. Data collected included the initial oxygen used on presentation (room air, nasal cannula, high flow oxygen, positive airway pressure, and intubation), age, body mass index, weight, temperature, blood pressure, pulse, oxygen saturation, respiratory rate, D-dimer, ferritin, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), C-reactive protein (CRP), total bilirubin, alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), serum white blood cell (WBC), hemoglobin (Hgb), creatinine. Treatments including Remdesivir, steroids, and convalescent plasma transfusion were recorded as well. Data was tracked at the time of presentation and 48 hours after (Table 1). The endpoint is 96 hours after the initial presentation or death in 30 days. Patients were separated into 2 groups based on their oxygen needs - high or low. The High Oxygen Needs Group included patients requiring either high flow oxygen, a PAP machine, or mechanical ventilation. The Low Oxygen Needs Group included patients on room air or nasal cannula. A total of 63 data points per chart are collected (Table 1, Figure 1)

The study sample was randomly split into training (70%, or 211 cases) and validation (30%, or 91 cases) sets to develop and test model performance using different unique seed numbers (2, 8, 24, 64, and 256) to assign the cases randomly per model. The classifier was developed within a JupyterLab environment, using Python as the programming language with XGBoost ensemble models for training. We leveraged libraries available to us in Python such as Matplotlib, Pandas, NumPy, and SciKitLearn to implement our data pipeline. The accuracy of our model was evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation in addition to the use of grid search to find optimal hyperparameters such as the learning rate, tree depth, etc. The external validation used only new data (24 cases) that the computer had not seen before to avoid overfitting, and this data was also de-identified. Five computer models are created using machine learning, random forest algorithms. Then, an ensemble prediction is calculated using the consensus of these five models.

Table 1 Data points collected from patient records.

Demographics	Data Collected Upon Arrival	Data Collected 48 Hours Later	Data Collected 96 Hours Later
Admission Date	Systolic blood pressure	Systolic blood pressure	Highest oxygen requirement at 96 hours
Age	Diastolic blood pressure	Diastolic blood pressure	Oxygen liter per minute used
Sex	Pulse	Pulse	Highest oxygen saturation
Ethnicity	Respiratory rate	Respiratory rate	CPAP or BiPAP usage
Zip Code	Room air saturation	Room air saturation	Intubation
	Temperature	Temperature	
Comorbidity	Body Mass Index		Other
Diabetes	Weight (kg)		Death within 30 days of presentation
Hypertension			
Coronary artery disease	Highest oxygen requirement within 4 hours of arrival	Highest oxygen requirement at 48 hours	
Heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF)	Oxygen liter per minute used	- Oxygen liter per minute used	
Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF)	Highest oxygen saturation	- Highest oxygen saturation	
Obstructive sleep apnea	CPAP or BiPAP usage	-CPAP or BiPAP usage	
Chronic lung disease	Intubation / mechanical ventilation	-Intubation / mechanical ventilation	
Immune suppressed			
Liver cirrhosis	Labs	Labs	
End stage renal disease on dialysis	HgbA1c (within 100 days of admission)		
	WBC	WBC	
Other Medical History	HGB	HGB	
Active smoker	Creatinine	Creatinine	
Former smoker	ALT	ALT	
Pregnancy	Tbili	Tbili	
	CRP	CRP	
	DDimer	DDimer	
	LDH	LDH	
	Ferritin	Ferritin	

Figure 1

IV. RESULTS

The study was conducted on cases beginning in September 2020, prior to the development of the SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. Out of the 302 cases reviewed, 55.6% are male, 44.4% are female. Additionally, 54.3% have diabetes, 61.6% have hypertension, 13.2% have a history of coronary artery disease, 2.0% have heart failure with reduced left ventricular ejection fraction 40% or lower (HFrEF), 8.9% have heart failure with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction greater than 40% (HFpEF), 14.2% have obstructive sleep apnea, 19.5% have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, 5.0% are on dialysis, 6.3% are active smokers and 24.5% are former smokers who quit greater than one year ago.

Initially, only 7.0 % were on CPAP / BiPAP and 0.3% were intubated on day 1 of hospital presentation. 12% of the patients required advanced oxygen support (mechanical ventilation, CPAP, BiPAP, and high flow oxygen) at time of presentation. At 48 hours from presentation, 45% of the patients needed advanced oxygen to stay alive. Overall, 12.9% died within 30 days from the initial presentation (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2

OUTCOME

80% were given Decadron, but only 44% received Remdesivir (due to a shortage of this medication) and 10.6% received convalescent plasma transfusion. Per the computer analysis, factors best correlated to oxygen needs at 96 hours after presentation are initial oxygen requirement and inflammatory markers such as CRP, LDH, ferritin, and D-dimer. Fever, weight, and body mass index (BMI) have a moderate correlation to oxygen needs at 96 hours of admission. Not surprisingly, Remdesivir use has no correlation to oxygen needs at 96 hours of admission, because Remdesivir does not affect mortality per RECOVERY Trial [2]. We also know that higher oxygen needs correlate to higher mortality [12]. Other data points including convalescent plasma transfusion, gender, and hypertension showed no effect on oxygen needs at 96 hours of admission. Interestingly, the models suggested that age is not a predictor of advanced oxygen need at 96 hours of admission during this early phase of the pandemic.

The 5 models yield the following accuracy results in terms of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and F1 scores with the 91 cases of training data: Model one - 0.87, 0.96, 0.95, 0.88, 0.91. Model two - 0.86, 0.91, 0.91, 0.90, 0.90. Model three - 0.75, 0.87, 0.85, 0.79, 0.80. Model four - 0.86, 0.94, 0.91, 0.91, 0.89. Model five - 0.82, 0.87, 0.86, 0.84, 0.84 (Table 2). The accuracy values of the ensemble model based on testing with the additional 24 cases not seen by the computer before are: 0.75, 0.94, 0.86, 0.88, 0.80.

Table 2

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Ensemble
Sensitivity	0.87	0.86	0.75	0.86	0.82	0.75
Specificity	0.96	0.91	0.87	0.94	0.87	0.94
Positive predictive value	0.95	0.91	0.85	0.91	0.86	0.86
Negative Predictive value	0.88	0.9	0.79	0.91	0.84	0.8
F1 Score	0.91	0.9	0.8	0.89	0.84	0.8

V. DISCUSSION

Even though this study lacks statistical significance, due to the small size of the test data, many of its findings correlate to our current understanding of SARS-CoV-29. For example, all five computer models suggest the use of Remdesivir has no effect on oxygen usage 96 hours after initial presentation. In the Adaptive COVID-19 Treatment Trial study (ACTT-1), Remdesivir decreases the length of hospital stay from 15 days to 10 days [22]. Therefore, Remdesivir is unlikely to affect the patient's hospital course and

oxygen usage on day 4 (96 hours). Remdesivir may affect oxygen usage by day 10. But on day 4, it's probably too early to notice any significant differences. Our models also suggest body mass index (BMI) is highly correlated to oxygen need on day 4, further confirmed by a study in South Africa [23].

Severely hospitalized SARS-CoV-2 patients commonly experience cytokine storms and systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) that are associated with adverse outcomes [24]. Therefore, it is not surprising to find our models suggest inflammatory markers such as D-Dimer, CRP, and ferritin to have a high correlation with a patient's oxygen needs 96 hours after presentation. (Table 3) Again, all five models suggest the patient's age does not have a significant impact on day 4 oxygen needs.

Table 3 Note that age has no significant correlation with increased oxygen need.

Models	Features of Importance					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
0 to 60 Oxy 1	26	38	33	44	169	310
CRP 1	25	26	37	32	136	256
CRP	21	23	29	29	62	164
LDH	24	19	31	27	49	150
Ferritin 1	25	16	36	21	19	117
DDimer 1	26	15	28	31	15	115
Ferritin	25		37	18	23	103
Temp	15	16	26	22	16	95
ALT 1			24	28	42	94
LDH 1	21	16		35	22	94
DDimer		19	22	20	27	88
WBC 1	16	19		17	35	87
BMI	15		24	26	19	84
Rm Air Sat				16	65	81
Creat 1			26	20	30	76
Creat	15		16		37	68
Weight	18		21		27	66
DBP			20	20	23	63
SBP 1			16	22	24	62
O2 Sat 1			15	18	26	59
Pulse 1	16		19	18		53
DBP 1	15			19	16	50
Temp 1			15		35	50
Pulse			22		26	48
WBC				19	22	41
0 to 60 Oxy	16		17			33
Resp 1				15	16	31
SBP		16		15		31
ALT				25		25
Tbili					22	22
Hgb 1			18			18
Remdesivir					18	18
Age				15		15

The samples in this study include data points recorded on day 2, or 48 hours, from the initial presentation. Then we used these data collected to predict a patient's oxygen needs on day 4, or 48 hours later the last data point was collected. This computer model gives us a 48-hours "Early Warning" of a patient's potential adverse disease progression (higher oxygen needs). Higher acuity beds like those in the intensive care unit (ICU) tend to have a higher nurse-to-patient ratio (1:2) as opposed to a regular medical ward's ratio (1:5). Patients on advanced oxygen support typically are housed in a unit of higher acute care like the ICU with a higher nurse-to-patient ratio. This model may help hospital administrators plan for their nursing staffing needs with a 48-hour lead time. This 48-hour lead time may be crucial to keep the hospital functioning at full capacity during SARS-CoV-2 surge time, when nursing staff can be difficult to find [25]. Patients with high oxygen demands are usually very ill, with increased risk of adult respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and death [8,9,11]. They are also bed-bound, requiring significant assistance from nursing staff.¹⁴ Therefore, higher oxygen needs imply greater nursing staff utilization and ICU transfer.

The data were collected during the alpha wave in late summer of 2020, before any variants emerged and vaccines were available. The current Omicron variant tends to be less virulent and milder than the alpha version [26]. Our model may not accurately predict a patient's oxygen needs with the current SARS-CoV-2 variant. Additionally, this computer model also does not account for vaccine usage which has significant efficacy against the virus [27]. Perhaps in the future, we can create a model that incorporates the effects of both vaccine usage and different variants.

Similar Study

A similar study by Alrajhi A. et al., is titled, "Data-Driven Prediction for COVID-19 Severity in Hospitalized Patients" [28]. This study also uses artificial intelligence to predict the severity of a SARS-CoV-2 infection. However, our study differs because we trained our model differently. Their model uses multi-class classification instead of binary classification. Their model estimates the level of severity rather than answering a binary, yes/no, question on whether a patient may need additional resources. It also shows multiple option strategies and compares the performance as shown by the ROC curves. Our paper solely focuses on boosting the ensemble model. Interestingly, their models produced calculated F1 scores between 0.77-0.94 while our ensemble model had an F1 score of 0.80. Our ensemble model achieved a similar accuracy to the multi-class classification model. This means that our simpler binary model worked as well as the more complex

model in the other study. This is significant because our simpler model is easier to train and has a lower cost of training.

In general, a neural network, machine-learning model needs a sample size of at least 1,000 samples [29]. Our model included data collected from only 302 patients. Therefore, its value has limitations. Additional data points are needed to make this model statistically significant. Our model holds up well to external data with a high F1-score, meaning comparable sensitivity and specificity. Our model may be ideal in this situation. It not only optimizes staff coverage while reducing unnecessary costs but also maximizes staffing ratios while still identifying patients that potentially require more resources. Because we observed similar results in the training and during the external data evaluating, we did not experience significant data overfitting issues that are common with smaller datasets [30-32].

Limitation Of Work

Due to the size of the external validation samples being too small (<40), we were unable to obtain a p-value to determine statistical significance. Through achieving more data this would allow for automation and improvement of accuracy. Aside from expanding the sample size, it would also be useful to conduct these studies through other programming languages aside from XGBoost. Other models we can consider are Tensorflow, Logistic Regression, Nearest Neighbor, and Naive Bayes. With more data, it would also provide more testing opportunities, allowing us to compare individual models and cross them with ensembles. We should also make further improvements that will make our program more user friendly by utilizing graphical user interface (GUI) instead of command line interface (CLI) and making the software available online, taking advantage of cloud computing. We would also like to do a retrospective analysis of outcome versus socioeconomic level. For example, we would like to consider the question: Do affected patients from poorer neighborhoods have a higher chance of requiring advanced oxygen than those patients from wealthier neighborhoods? This could be analyzed by identifying patients' zip codes and using the US census to extrapolate income and then comparing them to O2 requirement outcomes.

VI. CONCLUSION

It was extremely important for hospital administrators to manage and direct oxygen resources (ventilators, positive airway pressure machines, etc.) to the exact location of the greatest needs during the height of the pandemic. Patients on high flow oxygen, PAP, and ventilators consume vast amounts of ancillary and

nursing staff resources. Having a 48-hour advance alert would give hospital officials time to react and bring in the necessary oxygen, equipment, and nursing staff to accommodate the demand. While this model cannot accurately predict the outcome for individual patients, the model can provide group data to help hospital administrators plan the staffing of nurses, which is often restricted by California State regulations on nurse-to-patient ratios [33]. This simple proof of concept shows the potential use of computer models to help hospital administrators plan for staffing and resources needed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Unfortunately, this study lacks adequate sample sizes to increase its statistical powers for validity. Furthermore, this model was developed before vaccines were available and variants emerged. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention reports that unvaccinated individuals are 11 times more likely to suffer from SARS-CoV-2 than those fully vaccinated [34]. We have also seen how the introduction of vaccines affected the characteristics of hospitalized SARS-CoV-2 patients [17]. Due to these factors, this model is likely outdated. However, further training with new data points, including vaccination history, and the types of variants involved, would improve the accuracy of the model.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pons-Òdena M, et al.; COVID-19 and respiratory support devices. *Paediatr Respir Rev*. 2020 Sep;35:61-63. doi: 10.1016/j.prrv.2020.06.015. Epub 2020 Jun 20. PMID: 32690356; PMCID: PMC7305725.
- [2] Beigel JH, Tomashek KM, Dodd LE, Mehta AK, Zingman BS, Kalil AC, Hohmann E, Chu HY, Luetkemeyer A, Kline S, Lopez de Castilla D, Finberg RW, Dierberg K, Tapson V, Hsieh L, Patterson TF, Paredes R, Sweeney DA, Short WR, Touloumi G, Lye DC, Ohmagari N, Oh MD, Ruiz-Palacios GM, Benfield T, Fätkenheuer G, Kortepeter MG, Atmar RL, Creech CB, Lundgren J, Babiker AG, Pett S, Neaton JD, Burgess TH, Bonnett T, Green M, Makowski M, Osinusi A, Nayak S, Lane HC; ACTT-1 Study Group Members. Remdesivir for the Treatment of Covid-19 - Final Report. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Nov 5;383(19):1813-1826. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2007764. Epub 2020 Oct 8. PMID: 32445440; PMCID: PMC7262788.
- [3] Center for Disease Control and Prevention. Strategies to Mitigate Healthcare Personnel Staffing Shortages. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/mitigating-staff-shortages.html> (Accessed on May 13, 2022)
- [4] McIntosh K, Dees JH, Becker WB, Kapikian AZ, Chanock RM. Recovery in tracheal organ cultures of novel viruses from patients with respiratory disease. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 1967 Apr;57(4):933-40. doi: 10.1073/pnas.57.4.933. PMID: 5231356; PMCID: PMC224637
- [5] University of Minnesota Center for Infectious Disease Research and Policy. Estimates of SARS death rates revised upward. <https://www.cidrap.umn.edu/news-perspective/2003/05/estimates-sars-death-rates-revised-upward> (accessed on May 13, 2022)
- [6] World Health Organization. Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) . [https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/middle-east-respiratory-syndrome-coronavirus-\(mers-cov\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/middle-east-respiratory-syndrome-coronavirus-(mers-cov)) (accessed on May 13, 2022)
- [7] Zhang, Q., Bastard, P., COVID Human Genetic Effort. et al. Human genetic and immunological determinants of critical COVID-19 pneumonia. *Nature* 603, 587–598 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04447-0>.
- [8] Huang C, Wang Y, Li X, Ren L, Zhao J, Hu Y, Zhang L, Fan G, Xu J, Gu X, Cheng Z, Yu T, Xia J, Wei Y, Wu W, Xie X, Yin W, Li H, Liu M, Xiao Y, Gao H, Guo L, Xie J, Wang G, Jiang R, Gao Z, Jin Q, Wang J, Cao B. Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *Lancet*. 2020 Feb 15;395(10223):497-506. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5. Epub 2020 Jan 24. Erratum in: *Lancet*. 2020 Jan 30; PMID: 31986264; PMCID: PMC7159299.
- [9] Vahidy FS, Drews AL, Masud FN, Schwartz RL, Askary BB, Boom ML, Phillips RA. Characteristics and Outcomes of COVID-19 Patients During Initial Peak and Resurgence in the Houston Metropolitan Area. *JAMA*. 2020 Sep 8;324(10):998-1000. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.15301. PMID: 32789492; PMCID: PMC7426882.
- [10] Bhatraju PK, Ghassemieh BJ, Nichols M, Kim R, Jerome KR, Nalla AK, Greninger AL, Pipavath S, Wurfel MM, Evans L, Kritek PA, West TE, Luks A, Gerbino A, Dale CR, Goldman JD, O'Mahony S, Mikacenic C. Covid-19 in Critically Ill Patients in the Seattle Region - Case Series. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 May 21;382(21):2012-2022. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2004500. Epub 2020 Mar 30. PMID: 32227758; PMCID: PMC7143164.
- [11] Zhang Y, Gao Y, Qiao L, Wang W, Chen D. Inflammatory Response Cells During Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome in Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Ann Intern Med*. 2020 Sep 1;173(5):402-404. doi: 10.7326/L20-0227. Epub 2020 Apr 13. PMID:

- 32282871; PMID: PMC7175423.
- [12] Hasan SS, Capstick T, Ahmed R, Kow CS, Mazhar F, Merchant HA, Zaidi STR. Mortality in COVID-19 patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome and corticosteroids use: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Expert Rev Respir Med.* 2020 Nov;14(11):1149-1163. doi: 10.1080/17476348.2020.1804365. Epub 2020 Sep 29. PMID: 32734777; PMID: PMC7544968.
- [13] Wichmann D, Sperhake JP, Lütgehetmann M, Steurer S, Edler C, Heinemann A, Heinrich F, Mushumba H, Kniep I, Schröder AS, Burdelski C, de Heer G, Nierhaus A, Frings D, Pfefferle S, Becker H, Bredereke-Wiedling H, de Weerth A, Paschen HR, Sheikhzadeh-Eggers S, Stang A, Schmiedel S, Bokemeyer C, Addo MM, Aepfelbacher M, Püschel K, Kluge S. Autopsy Findings and Venous Thromboembolism in Patients With COVID-19: A Prospective Cohort Study. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020 Aug 18;173(4):268-277. doi: 10.7326/M20-2003. Epub 2020 May 6. PMID: 32374815; PMID: PMC7240772.
- [14] Iwamoto S, Johnstone M, Chiu M, Chu H. Acute Ischemic Stroke in a Young Woman with an Otherwise Asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 Infection. *J Med Res Surg* 2022 3(2): pp. 38-40. doi: 10.52916/jmrs224074
- [15] Ma L, Sahu SK, Cano M, et al. (2021) Increased complement activation is a distinctive feature of severe SARS-COV-2 infection. *Sci Immunol* 6(59): eabh2259.
- [16] Underlying medical conditions associated with higher risk for severe COVID-19: Information for Healthcare professionals. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/clinical-care/underlyingconditions.html>. Published February 15, 2022.
- [17] Muhar BK, Chu H, Zhou N. Retrospective Cross-Sectional Analysis of COVID-19 Patients in a Local Hospital During Delta Surge. *J Health Care and Research.* 2022 Apr 25;3(1):11-15.
- [18] Raveendran AV, Jayadevan R, Sashidharan S. Long COVID: An overview. *Diabetes Metab Syndr.* 2021 May-Jun;15(3):869-875. doi: 10.1016/j.dsx.2021.04.007. Epub 2021 Apr 20. Erratum in: *Diabetes Metab Syndr.* 2022 May 13;:102504. PMID: 33892403; PMID: PMC8056514.
- [19] Minshall D. Gulf War Syndrome: A review of current knowledge and understanding. *J R Nav Med Serv.* 2014;100(3):252-8. PMID: 25895403.
- [20] Prezant DJ. World Trade Center Cough Syndrome and its treatment. *Lung.* 2008;186 Suppl 1:S94-102. doi: 10.1007/s00408-007-9051-9. Epub 2007 Nov 20. PMID: 18027025.
- [21] Sacramento County Public Health. Number of hospitalized and ICU cases. <https://sac-epidemiology.maps.arcgis.com/apps/MapSeries/index.html?appid=e11bc926165742ab99f834079f618dad> (accessed on May 13, 2022).
- [22] Beigel JH, Tomashek KM, Dodd LE, Mehta AK, Zingman BS, Kalil AC, Hohmann E, Chu HY, Luetkemeyer A, Kline S, Lopez de Castilla D, Finberg RW, Dierberg K, Tapson V, Hsieh L, Patterson TF, Paredes R, Sweeney DA, Short WR, Touloumi G, Lye DC, Ohmagari N, Oh MD, Ruiz-Palacios GM, Benfield T, Fätkenheuer G, Kortepeter MG, Atmar RL, Creech CB, Lundgren J, Babiker AG, Pett S, Neaton JD, Burgess TH, Bonnett T, Green M, Makowski M, Osinusi A, Nayak S, Lane HC; ACTT-1 Study Group Members. Remdesivir for the Treatment of Covid-19 - Final Report. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Nov 5;383(19):1813-1826. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2007764. Epub 2020 Oct 8. PMID: 32445440; PMID: PMC7262788.
- [23] Soeroto AY, Soetedjo NN, Purwiga A, Santoso P, Kulsum ID, Suryadinata H, Ferdian F. Effect of increased BMI and obesity on the outcome of COVID-19 adult patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Metab Syndr.* 2020 Nov-Dec;14(6):1897-1904. doi: 10.1016/j.dsx.2020.09.029. Epub 2020 Sep 28. PMID: 33007661; PMID: PMC7521380.
- [24] Mehta P, McAuley DF, Brown M, Sanchez E, Tattersall RS, Manson JJ, HLH Across Speciality Collaboration, COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression, *Lancet.* 2020;395(10229):1033. Epub 2020 Mar 16.
- [25] Price S. An Overworked Force: Texas Grapples With Medical Staffing Shortage Amid COVID-19 Surge. *Tex Med.* 2021 Oct 1;117(10):30-33. PMID: 34855970.
- [26] Abdullah F, Myers J, Basu D, Tintinger G, Ueckermann V, Mathebula M, Ramlall R, Spoor S, de Villiers T, Van der Walt Z, Cloete J, Soma-Pillay P, Rheeder P, Paruk F, Engelbrecht A, Lalloo V, Myburg M, Kistan J, van Houghenouck-Tulleken W, Boswell MT, Gray G, Welch R, Blumberg L, Jassat W. Decreased severity of disease during the first global omicron variant covid-19 outbreak in a large hospital in Tshwane, South Africa. *Int J Infect Dis.* 2022 Mar;116:38-42. doi: 10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.357. Epub 2021 Dec 28. PMID: 34971823; PMID: PMC8713416.
- [27] Chen J, Wang R, Gilby NB, Wei GW. Omicron (B.1.1.529): Infectivity, vaccine breakthrough, and antibody resistance. *ArXiv [Preprint].* 2021 Dec 1;arXiv:2112.01318v1. Update in: *J Chem Inf Model.* 2022 Jan 24;62(2):412-422. PMID: 34873578; PMID: PMC8647651.

- [28] Alrajhi A, Alswailem O, Wali G, Alnafee K, AlGhamdi S, Alarifi J, Almuhaideb S, ElMoaqet H, AbuSalah A. Data-driven prediction for COVID-19 severity in hospitalized patients. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8910504/>. Published March 3, 2022.
- [29] Baum, E. B., & Haussler, D. What size net gives valid generalization?. *Neural computation*, 1989, 1(1), 151-160.
- [30] Alwosheel A, Cranenburgh Svan, Chorus CG. Is your dataset big enough? sample size requirements when using artificial neural networks for discrete choice analysis. *Journal of Choice Modeling*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocm.2018.07.002>.
- [31] Bartlett PL, Long PM. Failures of Model-dependent Generalization Bounds for Least-norm Interpolation. <https://mobile.jmlr.org/papers/volume22/20-1164/20-1164.pdf>. Published September 2021.
- [32] Takahashi Y, Ueki M, Tamiya G, Ogishima S, Kinoshita K, Hozawa A, Minegishi N, Nagami F, Fukumoto K, Otsuka K, Tanno K, Sakata K, Shimizu A, Sasaki M, Sobue K, Kure S, Yamamoto M, Tomita H. Machine learning for effectively avoiding overfitting is a crucial strategy for the genetic prediction of polygenic psychiatric phenotypes. *Transl Psychiatry*. 2020 Aug 17;10(1):294. doi: 10.1038/s41398-020-00957-5. PMID: 32826857; PMCID: PMC7442807.
- [33] Aiken LH, Sloane DM, Cimiotti JP, et al. Implications of the California nurse staffing mandate for other states. *Health Serv Res*. 2010;45(4):904-921. doi:10.1111/j.1475-6773.2010.01114.x
- [34] Scobie HM, Johnson AG, Suthar AB, Severson R, Alden NB, Balter S, Bertolino D, Blythe D, Brady S, Cadwell B, Cheng I, Davidson S, Delgadillo J, Devinnay K, Duchin J, Duwell M, Fisher R, Fleischauer A, Grant A, Griffin J, Haddix M, Hand J, Hanson M, Hawkins E, Herlihy RK, Hicks L, Holtzman C, Hoskins M, Hyun J, Kaur R, Kay M, Kidrowski H, Kim C, Komatsu K, Kugeler K, Lewis M, Lyons BC, Lyons S, Lynfield R, McCaffrey K, McMullen C, Milroy L, Meyer S, Nolen L, Patel MR, Pogojans S, Reese HE, Saupe A, Sell J, Sokol T, Sosin D, Stanislawski E, Stevens K, Vest H, White K, Wilson E, MacNeil A, Ritchey MD, Silk BJ. Monitoring Incidence of COVID-19 Cases, Hospitalizations, and Deaths, by Vaccination Status – 13 U.S. Jurisdictions, April 4–July 17, 2021. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*. 2021 Sep 17;70(37):1284-90. [PMID: 34529637]